

Modernization of legacy systems to microservice architecture using domain-driven design approach

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Review Protocol	1
2.1	Research Questions	1
2.2	Search Procedure	3
2.3	Study Selection	4
2.4	Keywording of Abstracts	5
2.5	Data Extraction and Mapping	6
2.6	Threats to validity	6
3	Report the Review	8
A	List of Primary Studies	10

1 Introduction

This study aims to establish a fair and broad overview of the modernization of legacy systems to microservice architecture using Domain-Driven Design (DDD). To do so, we have adopted the Systematic Mapping Study (SMS) technique proposed by Evidence-Based Software Engineering (EBSE). To conduct this SMS, we will follow the process proposed by [Petersen et al. \(2008, 2015\)](#). In short, this process is composed of five main steps, which will be detailed in the following sections:

- **Step 1 – Definition of Research Questions.** This step reports the research objectives for this systematic mapping. In short, a research protocol must have a pre-determined plan that describes research questions and guides how the systematic mapping must be conducted;
- **Step 2 – Conduction of Search.** This step describes how the primary studies must be searched and identified;
- **Step 3 – Screening of Papers.** This step reports how the identified studies must be evaluated according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria defined in this protocol;
- **Step 4 – Keywording of Abstracts.** This step shows how the included studies must be analyzed and classified; and
- **Step 5 – Data Extraction and Mapping of Studies.** This step describes how the final representation must be built, based on the final scheme created in Step 4.

2 Review Protocol

This section describes the protocol of the proposed SMS. In short, a research protocol is composed of a pre-determined plan that describes research questions and a guide to conduct the study. The essential process steps of a systematic mapping study are (i) definition of research questions; (ii) conducting the search for relevant papers; (iii) screening of papers; (iv) keywording of abstracts; (v) data extraction and mapping; and (vi) threats of validity. Next, we reported a description of each step.

2.1 Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to identify primary studies that report some evidence concerning modernization of legacy systems to microservice architecture using DDD. To do so, we established the following Research Questions (RQ):

RQ1: What are the demographic characteristics of the studies that presented an initiative on the modernization of legacy systems to the MSA style based on DDD?

The objective of this question is to establish a demographic overview of the initiatives identified in the literature to understand the relationship between publication venues and the maturity of the studies, for example. In this regard, four subquestions have been formulated:

- *When are the studies published?*
- *How are publications distributed between academia and industry?*
- *What is the maturity level of the publications?*

RQ2: What types of initiatives exist in the literature on the modernization of legacy systems to the MSA style using DDD?

The objective of this question is to identify these initiatives in order to later establish a taxonomy of them. As a result, this taxonomy is expected to serve as a reference for improving existing initiatives or proposing new ones.

RQ3: What is the core DDD concept that has been used in these initiatives?

The objective of this question is to identify which DDD concept has been utilized in the primary studies selected in this SMS. Additionally, it aims to assess the level of knowledge about DDD among the stakeholders (i.e., researchers and professionals). To achieve this, a subquestion has been formulated:

- *What is the level of DDD proficiency among the stakeholders?*

RQ4: Which application domains have been interested in this type of initiative?

The objective of this question is to map the application domains that have adopted solutions in the project of modernizing legacy systems to a microservices architecture based on the DDD approach.

RQ5: How has the DDD (Domain-Driven Design) approach been used in the modernization of legacy systems to a microservices architecture?

The objective of this question is to understand in which stage(s) (e.g., decomposition and development) the concept(s) of DDD have been used in the initiatives identified in this SMS.

RQ6: What are the motivating factors for adopting DDD in the modernization of legacy systems to a microservices architecture?

The objective of this question is to understand the motivations reported in the studies for conducting a modernization process based on DDD.

2.2 Search Procedure

Considering the RQs presented in [Section 2.1](#), we defined the search strategy, which is composed of source selection criteria, sources list, studies language, and keywords and their related terms.

- *Sources selection criteria:* We adopted the following criteria to select search sources (i.e., publication databases and search engines) to find primary studies: (i) content update (i.e., publications are regularly updated); (ii) availability (i.e., the full text of the papers are available); (iii) quality of results (i.e., the accuracy of the results returned by the search); and (iv) versatility to export the results (i.e., since much information are returned through the search, a mechanism to export the results is required) ([Dieste et al., 2009](#));
- *Sources list:* The publication databases selected in our study are shown in [Table 1](#). The ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, Science Direct, SpringerLink, Web of Science, and Scopus is an efficient set of publication databases, namely the most used in computer science and widely used in the context of software engineering ([Petersen et al., 2015](#)). To avoid missing any relevant study, we applied the backward snowballing technique to the selected studies (i.e., second phase), and included the subsequent results as gray literature in our SMS ([Petersen et al., 2015](#)).

Table 1: Selected Databases

Source	Location
ACM Digital Library	dl.acm.org
IEEE Xplore	www.ieeexplore.ieee.org
ScienceDirect	www.sciencedirect.com
Scopus	www.scopus.com
SpringerLink	https://link.springer.com
Web of Science	www.isiknowledge.com

- *Studies language:* Only primary studies written in English will be considered in this systematic mapping, since it is the most common language in scientific papers;
- *Keywords:* “DDD” and “microservice”, with the following related terms:
 - **DDD:** “DDD” OR “Domain Driven Design” OR “Domain-Driven Design”
 - **microservice:** “micro service” OR “micro services” OR “micro-service” OR “micro-services” OR “microservice” OR “microservices”

- *Search string*: We identified two terms related to known keywords to answer the RQs, namely: systematic literature review and microservice. We used the Boolean operator OR to link the main terms and their synonyms, and the Boolean operator AND to combine these terms, as shown in [Table 2](#).

Table 2: SaS search string

("DDD" OR "Domain Driven Design" OR "Domain-Driven Design")
AND
("micro service" OR "micro services" OR "micro-service" OR "micro-services" OR "microservice" OR "microservices")

2.3 Study Selection

Another important element of planning is to define the Inclusion Criteria (IC) and Exclusion Criteria (EC). These criteria enable us to include primary studies that are relevant to answer the research questions and exclude studies that do not answer them. Thus, we defined one inclusion criterion for our SMS, namely:

- **IC1**: The primary study presents some evidence about the modernization of legacy systems to microservice architecture using DDD.

This criterion (IC1) serves as the basis for our selection of relevant studies for this review. According to our investigation, "modernization" is a comprehensive term specifically applied to microservices. This evidence indicates that it may encompass concepts such as decomposition, migration, modernization, reengineering, and transition. In short, these synonyms denote efforts aimed at transitioning a legacy system to the microservices architecture. Similarly, it is equally important to outline our exclusion criteria. The exclusion criteria established are:

- **EC1**: the study did not involve the modernization of legacy systems to microservices architecture using DDD;
- **EC2**: the study is an editorial, position paper, keynote speech, opinion, tutorial, poster, or panel;
- **EC3**: the study is not written in English;
- **EC4**: the study only provides a summary or is not available in full-length;
- **EC5**: the study is similar to previous work developed by the same author. Here, only the most recent study or the most complete version must be considered; and
- **EC6**: the study is a tertiary study.

2.4 Keywording of Abstracts

Figure 1 summarizes the conduction phases of our study, also showing the number of selected studies at the end of each one. Initially, **Phase 0**, it is possible to observe the total number of studies returned by the search strings, as well as the number returned for each publication base (ACM – 8, IEEE – 48, Science Direct – 5, Springer – 229, Web of Science – 48, and Scopus – 94). As we encountered duplicate studies within the databases, prompting our first refinement step, which involved removing these duplicates, resulting in 439 studies. Subsequently, we filtered out any studies that did not meet the criteria for primary studies, resulting in 438 studies (**Phase 1**). Next, we unified all the studies into a single file and eliminated any duplicate studies that were found in more than one database, resulting in 438 studies (**Phase 2**). Besides eliminating duplicates, this phase focused on selecting only primary studies with a research theme related to modernization for microservice architecture. This strategy enables a more directed exploration of modernization-related facets, aligning with the objectives of our study. As can be seen in **Phase 3**, we selected 61 studies for full reading after apply our selection criteria. Regarding this phase, it is worth highlighting that divergences in criteria were resolved through discussion among review participants to standardize inclusion or exclusion from the study. After carefully reading the 61 studies, we selected 45 to compose the final list of our tertiary study (**Phase 4**). [Appendix A](#) shows the list of primary studies selected in our mapping.

Figure 1: Conduction phases of our study

To increase the reliability of our results, we reviewed all the studies selected before

proceeding to the data synthesis (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007). The forms (see Table 3 – Section 2.5) filled in the second selection were analyzed again and, whenever necessary, important parts of each study or its full text were read to identify potential classification errors. During the review, we extracted more information from some studies, particularly the ones that did not have enough information extracted in the previous step, and did not remove any study, maintaining the 45 primary studies selected.

2.5 Data Extraction and Mapping

During the data collection phase, we will collect a set of variables that describe each primary study. Data collection is going to be handled by members of the team and conflicts will be resolved by a supervisor. Each researcher involved will perform data extraction for every primary study separately. Then the two values of each variable obtained by each researcher will be compared to each other and the final value of the variable will be assigned to the primary study after a discussion on every researcher's opinion. If both researchers assigned the same value to one variable, we will assign this value to the variable without further discussion. On the other hand, after a debate among the researchers and their supervisor, a value will be assigned to each variable. We will not apply an agreement measure as the number of researchers involved in the review is not significantly large. However, all conflicts will be recorded. We extracted assigned values to the attributes for each study, as presented in Table 3.

The first three data items are going to be used for documentation reasons. These data items and the remaining items are going to be used for answering the research questions of this study. We must use a synthesis or analysis data method in each answer.

2.6 Threats to validity

To enhance the trustworthiness of our study and reduce the biases that could be inserted by authors of the selected studies, we report and discuss the main aspects that might represent threats to validity, and the actions performed to mitigate them. We have strictly followed the guidelines proposed by Kitchenham and Charters (2007), Kitchenham et al. (2010), Petersen et al. (2008), and Petersen et al. (2015) to achieve an impartial review. These guidelines have been widely adopted in SLR, surveys, and SMS (Filisbino Passini et al., 2022; Souza et al., 2018; Wedyan and Abufakher, 2020; Zavala et al., 2019). Next, a description of the threats of our study is reported:

Omission of papers. As reported in Section 2.2, four publication databases were used to extract the data analyzed in this paper. According to Dybå et al. (2007), Kitchenham and Charters (2007), and Petersen et al. (2015), such databases are sufficient

Table 3: Data extraction form

Research Topic	Description	RQ
ID	Integer	-
Source	Publication database name	-
Article title	Title of the article	-
Author Name	Set of names of the authors	-
Institutions	Name(s) of institution(s) of the author(s)	-
Author's country	Country of each author	-
Year	Calendar year	RQ1.1
Nature	Academic, Industrial, or Mixed	RQ1.2
Maturity level	Maturity level in the evaluation process	RQ1.3
Initiative's name	Initiative's name in literature	RQ2
Concept from	DDD base concept that has been used in these initiatives	RQ3
Domains	Domain and/or subdomain where the study is inserted	RQ4
Use stage	How the DDD approach has been applied	RQ5
Motivations	Motivations before modernization	RQ6

and the most relevant sources in the software engineering area. Despite our efforts to make this process as reliable as possible, it is still possible that primary studies were missed and not reported. Although we have conducted evaluations to calibrate and ensure the efficiency of our search string, our study depends on the search engines of each research database. Thus, in order to minimize problems in the search phase, we adapted the general search string to meet the constraints/limitations of each publication database.

Reviewers' reliability. Only one research was responsible for the conduction of our study, which can result in bias risk. Therefore, to ensure the reliability of our study and that it was conducted unbiasedly, software engineering specialists supported the researcher in this process during the conduction meeting to solve questions as to the inclusion or exclusion of studies. Moreover, none of the primary studies included was developed by our research group or researchers related to us. Therefore, we are not aware of any bias we may have introduced during the analysis.

Data extraction. We have analyzed or interpreted data extracted from the primary studies because not all data was clear. Since this activity involves human judgment, we

rigorously followed our research protocol (see [Section 2.2](#)), and defined a form for data extraction based on our RQs. To ensure the validity of our study, we analyzed other information sources, such as technical reports, websites, and manuals.

Replicability. We report the process used to conduct the mapping in [Section 2.2](#) to make our study replicable. Since we are using electronic databases to collect all data and these databases are constantly being updated, the results might not be identical in a future search. Therefore, replicating this mapping can be considered a not trivial task, but the periodic update can assist the stakeholders in monitoring and evolution of a research area.

3 Report the Review

We will report the following items in our study: (i) discuss findings: we will report the description of primary studies, results of any quantitative summaries, and details of any meta-analysis; (ii) present a discussion: we will summarize the principal findings, strengths and weaknesses of the mapping, and the meaning of findings, such as applicability, benefits, adverse effects, and risks; (iii) discuss conclusions: we will report the recommendations, such as practical implications for software development, implications for practitioners, and unanswered questions and implications for future research; and (iv) discuss limitation: we will synthesize the limitations of this study.

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A List of Primary Studies

Table 4 lists the primary studies included in the SMS described in Appendix A. The ID column presents the study identifiers. The Reference column displays the author(s) and title, along with an external link to the online reference for each study. Finally, the Year column shows the publication years of the studies.

Table 4: List of Primary Studies

ID	Reference	Year
S1	Vural, Hulya and Koyuncu, Murat and Misra, Sanjay, A Case Study on Measuring the Size of Microservices.	2018
S2	Saidi, Malak and Tissaoui, Anis and Faiz, Sami, A DDD Approach Towards Automatic Migration To Microservices.	2023
S3	Wijaya, I Gede Rahmat and Fajar, Ahmad Nurul, A Design Study of Microservice Architecture on White Label Travel Platform.	2023
S4	Wang, Yanze and Li, Shanshan and Liu, Huikun and Zhang, He and Pan, Bo, A Reference Architecture for Blockchain-based Traceability Systems Using Domain-Driven Design and Microservices.	2022
S5	Joselyne, Munezero Immaculee and Bajpai, Gaurav and Nzanywayingoma, Frederic, A Systematic Framework of Application Modernization to Microservice based Architecture.	2021
S6	Camilli, Matteo and Colarusso, Carmine and Russo, Barbara and Zimeo, Eugenio, Actor-Driven Decomposition of Microservices through Multi-level Scalability Assessment.	2023
S7	P, Isha V and H, Vishalakshmi Prabhu, An Approach to Clean Architecture for Microservices Using Python.	2023
S8	Diepenbrock, Andreas and Rademacher, Florian and Sachweh, Sabine, An Ontology-based Approach for Domain-driven Design of Microservice Architectures.	2017
S9	Lie, Reynaldi and Fajar, Ahmad Nurul, ANALYSIS AND DEVELOPMENT OF MICROSERVICES ARCHITECTURE IN LOAN APPLICATION SYSTEM OF COOPERATIVE ENTERPRISE IN INDONESIA.	2022
S10	Macías, Aurora and Navarro, Elena and Cuesta, Carlos E. and Zdun, Uwe, Architecting Digital Twins Using a Domain-Driven Design-Based Approach.	2023
S11	Zhou, Xiaolong and Xiong, Jingliu, Automated Microservice Identification from Design Model.	2022

Continua na próxima página

ID	Referência	Ano
S12	De Alwis, Adambarage Anuruddha Chathuranga and Barros, Alistair and Fidge, Colin and Polyvyanyy, Artem, Business Object Centric Microservices Patterns.	2019
S13	Rademacher, Florian and Sorgalla, Jonas and Sachweh, Sabine, Challenges of Domain-Driven Microservice Design: A Model-Driven Perspective.	2018
S14	Apitchaka Singjai and Uwe Zdun, Conformance assessment of Architectural Design Decisions on API endpoint designs derived from domain models.	2022
S15	Singjai, Apitchaka and Zdun, Uwe, Conformance Assessment of Architectural Design Decisions on the Mapping of Domain Model Elements to APIs and API Endpoints.	2022
S16	Rademacher, Florian and Sachweh, Sabine and Zündorf, Albert, Deriving Microservice Code from Underspecified Domain Models Using DevOps-Enabled Modeling Languages and Model Transformations.	2020
S17	Vural, Hulya and Koyuncu, Murat, Does Domain-Driven Design Lead to Finding the Optimal Modularity of a Microservice?.	2021
S18	Kapferer, Stefan and Zimmermann, Olaf, Domain-Driven Architecture Modeling and Rapid Prototyping with Context Mapper.	2021
S19	Praschl, Christoph and Bauernfeind, Sophie and Leitner, Christian and Zwettler, Gerald A., Domain-Driven Design as Model Contract in Full-Stack Development.	2023
S20	Alsolami, Fawaz, Domain-Driven Microservice Architecture for Designing Modern Applications.	2020
S21	Kapferer, Stefan and Zimmermann, Olaf, Domain-driven service design context modeling, model refactoring and contract generation.	2020
S22	Kapferer, Stefan and Zimmermann, Olaf, Domain-specific Language and Tools for Strategic Domain-driven Design, Context Mapping and Bounded Context Modeling.	2020
S23	Zhong, Chenxing and Zhang, He and Huang, Huang and Chen, Zhikun and Li, Chao and Liu, Xiaodong and Li, Shanshan, DOMICO: Checking conformance between domain models and implementations.	2024
S24	Zaschke, Christian, Elaboration of a Domain Model for Migrating the Monolithic Software Architecture of a Data Management Server into a Microservice Architecture.	2019

ID	Referência	Ano
S25	Telnov, Yury, Enterprise product and service process design with the use of intelligent technologies.	2019
S26	Ding, Yu and Wang, LiLing and Li, Shaokun and Wang, XuTong and Zhang, JianWei, Enterprise service application architecture based on Domain Driven Model Design.	2020
S27	Farsi, Hassan and Allaki, Driss and En-nouaary, Abdeslam and Dahchour, Mohamed, Following Domain Driven Design principles for Microservices decomposition: is it enough?.	2021
S28	De Alwis, Adambarage Anuruddha Chathuranga and Barros, Alistair and Polyvyanyy, Artem and Fidge, Colin, Function-Splitting Heuristics for Discovery of Microservices in Enterprise Systems.	2018
S29	Ivas, Ivka, Implementation of Composable Enterprise in an Evolutionary Way Through Holistic Business-IT Delivery of Business Initiatives: Real Industry Use Case.	2024
S30	Suryana, T. and Bachtiar, A. M. and Budi, C. S., Implementation of Micro Services Architecture on Comrades Backend.	2019
S31	Giallorenzo, Saverio and Montesi, Fabrizio and Peressotti, Marco and Rademacher, Florian, LEMMA2Jolie: A tool to generate microservice APIs from domain models.	2023
S32	Deljouyi, Amirhossein and Ramsin, Raman, MDD4REST: Model-Driven Methodology for Developing RESTful Web Services.	2022
S33	Krause, Alexander and Zirkelbach, Christian and Hasselbring, Wilhelm and Lenga, Stephan and Kröger, Dan, Microservice Decomposition via Static and Dynamic Analysis of the Monolith.	2020
S34	Ma, Shang-Pin and Li, Chia-Yu and Lee, Wen-Tin and Lee, Shin-Jie, Microservice Migration Using Strangler Fig Pattern and Domain-Driven Design.	2022
S35	Li, Chia-Yu and Ma, Shang-Pin and Lu, Tsung-Wen, Microservice Migration Using Strangler Fig Pattern: A Case Study on the Green Button System.	2020
S36	Rahmatulloh, Alam and Sari, Dewi Wulan and Shofa, Rahmi Nur and Darmawan, Irfan, Microservices-based IoT Monitoring Application with a Domain-driven Design Approach.	2021
S37	Haferkorn, Daniel and Rodenbeck, Roland and Kerth, Christian and Zschke, Christian, Migration from Monolith to Microservices with Legacy Compatibility.	2020

ID	Referência	Ano
S38	Steinegger, Roland H. and Giessler, Pascal and Hippchen, Benjamin and Abeck, Sebastian, Overview of a Domain-Driven Design Approach to Build Microservice-Based Applications.	2017
S39	Josélyne, Munezero Immaculée and Tuheirwe-Mukasa, Doreen and Kanagwa, Benjamin and Balikuddembe, Joseph, Partitioning microservices: a domain engineering approach.	2018
S40	Singjai, Apitchaka and Zdun, Uwe and Zimmermann, Olaf and Pautasso, Cesare, Patterns on Deriving APIs and their Endpoints from Domain Models.	2022
S41	Özkan, Ozan and Babur, Önder and van den Brand, Mark, Refactoring with domain-driven design in an industrial context: An action research report.	2023
S42	Bai, Rui and Fang, Zhou and Ma, Chao and Huang, Hai and Wanjuan, Xie, Research on the Forecast of Workshop Production Abnormity under Cloud Manufacturing Environment.	2021
S43	Gysel, Michael and Kölbener, Lukas and Giersche, Wolfgang and Zimmermann, Olaf, Service Cutter: A Systematic Approach to Service Decomposition.	2016
S44	Liu, Lisi and Yao, Yingxue and Li, Jianguang, Service-oriented invisible numerical control application: architecture, implementation, and test.	2022
S45	Fritzsche, Jonas and Bogner, Justus and Haug, Markus and Wagner, Stefan and Zimmermann, Alfred, Towards an Architecture-Centric Methodology for Migrating to Microservices.	2024